

Researching the British East India Company Using Soldiers' Letters Published in British Newspapers 1780-1857

Research Guide

Abstract

This research guide is designed to assist in the identification and analysis of soldiers' letters in British newspapers. The author is a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellow at LMU Munich. These findings are based on a two-year research project on the nineteenth-century army serving in India.

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1. Why use this guide?

If we want to understand contemporary attitudes to imperial expansion in Britain, we need to consider the sources of information that were available to people at the time. Soldiers' letters were one of the main ways in which the reading public learned about overseas military operations during this period.

This guide will help you to identify and analyse these letters for the purposes of historical research.

2. What are letters from the front?

Soldiers serving overseas wrote letters describing their campaign experiences. Some of these letters were published in British newspapers.

Most of these letters were originally addressed to friends and family in Britain who then submitted them to British newspaper editors for publication. Often this happened without the letter-writer's permission. Keep in mind, however, that even soldiers who did not intend for their letter to become public were aware of the possibility that it might appear in print, or, at the very least, that it might be shared with friends, family, and prospective patrons.

Letters could appear in newspapers in different forms. Sometimes the editor summarized the contents of a soldiers' letter without quoting from it at length. At other times, the letter was excerpted or even reprinted in full.

3. Who wrote these letters?

Archival evidence suggests that soldiers of all ranks wrote letters to friends and family, but not all these letters were published.

Most letters that appeared in newspapers were published anonymously.

Although the editor did not normally provide the author's name, they usually indicated the author's rank, regiment, and where they were writing from.

In the eighteenth and early nineteenth century, most letters printed in newspapers were authored by officers. Because of their gentlemanly status and insider access, officers were considered to be a more reliable source of information about military operations.

As the nineteenth century progressed, rank and file soldiers featured more prominently in British newspapers. This transformation reflects a growing demand for 'human interest' stories, particularly in the provincial press. Editors wanted readers to be able to experience war from the perspective of the average person.

4. Genre and style

Letters were written to inform but also to entertain. This is true even of letters that were not intended for publication. Soldiers always wrote with an audience in mind, even if it was just an audience of one.

Soldiers' letters borrow from the literary conventions of the time. This means that soldiers' letters typically possess many of the features of sentimental novels, including the frequent appearance of damsels in distress. Others resemble travel narratives, which exoticize the people and places that they claim to describe.

Remember that letters are not always strictly factual. Sometimes, letter-writers would embellish and invent. Even if they are inaccurate, however, letters can tell us something about how war was conceptualized and discussed during this period.

5. What do these letters reveal?

Soldiers wrote on many different topics, but most published letters relate to one or more of the following themes:

- Conditions of service, including long marches and life in camp
- Foreign people and places
- Troop movements and battle tactics
- Combat experiences

Many letters present a heroic portrait of military service. Others are critical. Most criticisms are directed at commanding officers and/or military authorities; these criticisms usually cite evidence of mismanagement, incompetence, or corruption. A significant minority of these letters relate to alleged breaches of military convention, typically concerning violence against women and children or prisoners of war.

6. Strengths and weaknesses

Strengths

Soldiers' letters are particularly good sources for the conflicts of the mid-nineteenth century. Letters were more likely to be printed in full. Newspapers also featured a wider variety of military personnel, including the rank and file.

Certain conflicts excited considerable interest in Britain and therefore received greater newspaper coverage. Letters from the First Anglo-Afghan War (1839-1842), the First Anglo-Sikh War (1845-1846), and the Second Anglo-Sikh War (1849-1850) are well represented in the newspaper archive.

Through this newspaper coverage, we can access letters that would not have survived otherwise. This is particularly true of letters written by the rank and file in the nineteenth century, which are not preserved in large numbers in traditional archives.

Weaknesses

The newspapers of the eighteenth century prioritized elite perspectives; most letters were written by officers. These letters were usually synthesized by the editor rather than printed in full. These letters can also be hard to identify in online databases due to lower-quality OCR (Optical Character Recognition) and the infrequent use of headings.

Not all conflicts were covered equally. European conflicts were usually given precedence over imperial campaigns. The Second Anglo-Maratha War (1803-5, 6) was overshadowed by the Napoleonic Wars (1799-1815) and did not feature very prominently in British newspapers, for example.

Soldiers' letters represent a male perspective. In the nineteenth century, newspapers did also publish letters by European women, usually the wives of military officers or missionaries. These letters can provide a useful complement to soldiers' letters by showing how women's ways of experiencing and writing about war may have differed from men's.

The letters that feature in British newspapers during this period were authored by Europeans. Although large numbers of South Asians served in the EIC's armies, South Asian perspectives are largely absent from British newspaper coverage during this period.

7. Where can these letters be found?

The British Library (BL) is the primary repository for historical newspapers in Britain. In 2004, the BL began digitizing their collections. These digitized collections can be accessed through three main databases:

- *Burney Newspapers Collection* is comprised of newspapers from the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries and was produced in partnership with Gale, a Cengage Company; it can be accessed in BL reading rooms or by institutional subscription.
- *British Library's 19th Century Newspapers* was produced in partnership with Gale, a Cengage Company; it can be accessed in BL reading rooms or by institutional subscription.
- *British Newspaper Archive* consists primarily of nineteenth-century newspapers and includes many provincial publications; it was produced in partnership with findmypast, an online genealogy service. This database is available in BL reading rooms or by private subscription.

Note that the *Times*, a leading and politically influential newspaper for the period 1785-1855, is not part of these collections. *The Times Digital Archive*, a Gale product, is available for the period 1785-2019 through a separate institutional subscription.

8. Understanding the newspaper archive

As a legal deposit library, the BL is entitled to a copy of every UK print publication. In theory, the BL has a copy of every newspaper published in Britain since 1869, when newspapers were first included within this legal deposit legislation. The BL has also inherited the newspapers that were collected by the Stamp Office between 1820 and 1869, when publishers were required to submit copies for the purposes of taxation. Prior to 1820, newspapers were not systematically collected, and what survives was largely compiled by private individuals; for example, the *Burney Newspaper Collections* are so named because they represent an augmented version of the private collection of Rev. Charles Burney (1757-1817).

9. Tips for searching

Digitized historical newspapers have been processed into machine-readable text to enable searching; however, this text is not usually an exact copy of the original. Words may be missing or misspelled. A keyword search might not return any results, but this does not necessarily indicate an absence of relevant material.

A few common phrases used by editors to introduce soldiers' letters include:

- "By a private letter from India"
- "A letter from an officer"
- "Letter of an officer"
- "Letters to friends at home"

The editor will often specify the regiment or the name of the commanding officer. Campaign narratives and regimental histories are good sources for identifying these keywords. To assist in this process, consult the annotated bibliography referenced in the Online Resources section of this research guide.

Using people or place names as search terms can be effective, but keep in mind the lack of standardized spelling for this period. This applies particularly to South Asian people and places. You may find it helpful to use a wildcard. A question mark(?) can be used to represent a single character anywhere in the word, helping you to include variable spellings. For example, searching 'Marat?a' would return both Maratha and Maratta.

You may wish to browse or filter by date. Remember that travel time between Britain and India could be as long as six months; a significant period could elapse between the moment when an event occurred and the date when news was received in Britain.

Headlines were used unevenly during this period; the headline 'War in India' is often used, but otherwise you might have to dig through unmarked paragraphs for relevant passages.

10. Complementary primary sources

Soldiers' letters were not the only source of military intelligence available to domestic audiences. Other sources commonly cited in newspapers include:

- Official dispatches printed in the London Gazette (typically considered the most authentic source of news)
- Foreign newspapers (often French and Dutch)
- Letters written by diplomatic agents, colonial officials, or other people living and working abroad
- News transmitted orally by ship's captains or travelling merchants

Some soldiers' letters were debated in parliament. Prior to 1771, journalists were forbidden from reporting on parliamentary proceedings; thereafter, parliamentary proceedings featured prominently in British newspapers. You can also find records of parliamentary debates using these databases:

- For the period 1803-2005, parliamentary debates can be found on the Hansard database for free (see online resources, below).
- For the period 1774-1805, records of parliamentary debates were published in the *Parliamentary Register*. Individual volumes can be found on Google Books, Hathi Trust, and the Internet Archive.
- Both Hansard and the *Parliamentary Register* can be accessed on the *UK Parliamentary Papers* database by those with an institutional subscription.

Unpublished soldiers' letters are concentrated in a few key archives. These include: the British Library, London; the National Army Museum, London; the Centre for South Asian Studies Archive, Cambridge; the National Library of Scotland, Edinburgh; and the National Archives of Scotland, Edinburgh.

11. Online resources

British Library Newspapers. Gale. <https://www.gale.com/intl/primary-sources/british-library-newspapers>

British Newspaper Archive. Findmypast. <https://www.britishnewspaperarchive.co.uk/>

Hansard. UK Parliament. <https://hansard.parliament.uk/>

HathiTrust Digital Library. University consortium. <https://www.hathitrust.org/>

Hobson-Jobson: A Glossary of Colloquial Anglo-Indian Words and Phrases. Digital Dictionaries of South Asia. <https://dsal.uchicago.edu/dictionaries/hobsonjobson/>

Seventeenth- and Eighteenth-Century Burney Newspapers Collection. Gale. <https://www.gale.com/intl/c/17th-and-18th-century-burney-newspapers-collection>

The Atlas of Digitised Newspapers and Metadata. Beals, M. H. and Emily Bell, with contributions by Ryan Cordell, Paul Fyfe, Isabel Galina Russell, Tessa Hauswedell, Clemens Neudecker, Julianne Nyhan, Sebastian Padó, Miriam Peña Pimentel, Mila

Oiva, Lara Rose, Hannu Salmi, Melissa Terras, and Lorella Viola.

<https://www.digitisednewspapers.net/>

UK Parliamentary Papers. ProQuest. <https://parlipapers.proquest.com>

12. Recommended reading

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Pratt, Mary Louise. *Imperial Eyes: Travel Writing and Transculturation*. 2nd ed. London: Routledge, 2008.

Ramsey, Neil. *The Military Memoir and Romantic Literary Culture, 1780-1835*. Farnham: Ashgate, 2011.

Roy, Kaushik. *War, Culture and Society in Early Modern South Asia, 1740-1849*. London: Routledge, 2011.

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Sutherland, Lucy S. *The East India Company in Eighteenth-Century Politics*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1952.

Welsch, Christina. *The Company's Sword: The East India Company and the Politics of Militarism, 1644–1858*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2022.

13. Project details

This research guide is based on research findings from a two-year postdoctoral project, entitled *Bearing Witness in Wartime: East India Company Soldiers in the British Public Domain, 1750-1857*. In the eighteenth century, a British trading corporation called the East India Company (EIC) began to build a territorial empire in India through a process of violent conquest. To fight these wars of imperial expansion, the EIC formed their own standing armies, which they deployed alongside British Army regiments. Because the EIC's commercial monopoly restricted British access to the subcontinent, these military personnel were an

important source of information for domestic audiences in Britain. War correspondents did not yet exist, so soldiers' testimony represented the primary alternative to the official narratives disseminated in government gazettes. Soldiers published books and pamphlets, and their letters appeared in newspapers and periodicals. This project's overall research objective is to determine what soldiers disclosed and what impact this had on contemporary debates about the EIC's military operations.

To achieve this objective, this research critically analyses a combination of print and manuscript materials. Using military records and manuals of military law, it reconstructs the regulatory frameworks in operation in the nineteenth century. Professional conduct within the armies was regulated by the Articles of War laid down by the king or queen, while parliament voted on the Mutiny Act: the code of law that defined and regulated more serious crimes. Supplementing this were orders issued to the army by different authorities including the Secretary of State for War, the Commander in Chief, the Adjutant General and his Deputy, and the Quarter Master General. Using these sources, it becomes possible to understand the incentives and disincentives that informed soldiers' decision to write. Court martial records, read alongside published and unpublished letters authored by soldiers, provide additional insights into their decisions to approach the press with their stories.

The main sources for this project are the writings of soldiers themselves, which took the form of books, pamphlets, and published letters in newspapers and periodicals. To evaluate the impact of these writings on public debate, this project examines how contemporaries responded in editorials and letters to the editor, as well as how soldiers' testimony was cited by MPs in parliament. By contrasting soldiers' testimony with official dispatches in government gazettes, it becomes possible to identify how soldiers challenged or supplemented official government narratives. In all, this research demonstrates that soldiers played an important part in the information environment of eighteenth- and nineteenth-century Britain.

14. Project identity

Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-PF-01

Project Number: 101065824

Project Acronym: WAR_WITNESS

Project Title: Bearing Witness in Wartime: The East India Company's Soldiers in the Public Domain, 1764-1857

Fellow's Name: Dr Callie Wilkinson

Supervisor's Name: Prof Dr Roland Wenzlhuemer

Host Institution: Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich

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